

THE PEDAGOGICAL MODEL FOR DEVELOPING COGNITIVE ACTIVITY IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the pedagogical model of the process of developing cognitive activity in primary students, its purpose, structure, components and the importance of this model in the educational process, as well as the stages of implementation.*

Keywords: *diagnostic stage, Target-developmental stage, activity and reflection stage, Monitoring and Correction stage, Target-motivational component, activity-meaningful component, technological component, consequential component.*

INTRODUCTION

Many teachers have difficulty finding or creating materials for students to use outside of class. However, the effectiveness of the flipped classroom model largely depends on the activities that take place during class. Therefore, it is recommended to first organize class time meaningfully and then work on the resources provided as homework. In this model, the amount of extracurricular work of students increases. If students do not understand that this independent work serves to improve their learning activities in the classroom, this may cause dissatisfaction.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of "cognitive activity" is complex in content, and it is specialized in relation to the general concept of "activity", that is, it is oriented towards a certain direction. By its nature, it is a type of mental activity aimed at cognitive processes, that is, knowledge, understanding, thinking, perception and conscious learning.

In pedagogical and psychological literature, this concept is often used to express internally motivated and purposeful cognitive actions of a student involved in educational activities. In scientific research, "activity" is interpreted as a general scientific concept and is studied in many areas - in philosophy, psychology, pedagogy - in connection with activity. In particular, in philosophical sources, "activity" (from the French "activité" - "power of action") is interpreted as a category expressing the nature of man as an active being, his active and changing attitude to the outside world [4].

From a psychological point of view, activity is recognized as a necessary condition for the existence of living beings, that is, as an internal state that has its own source of action. An active subject manifests itself as a being that does not simply react to external influences, but embodies the internal motivational source of its activity. According to A.N. Leontiev, activity is not a reactive state to external stimuli, but an active state organized by the subject on the basis of internal needs and motives [5].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research used methods of comparative study of scientific, methodological, pedagogical literature, sources, SDS, qualification requirements, curriculum, long-term plan, subject programs,

textbooks, domestic and foreign experience, observation, interviews, questionnaires, experimental test work, mathematical and statistical analysis of the results.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

A pedagogical model of the process of development of cognitive activity of primary school students has been developed on a theoretical and practical basis. The purpose of the model is to develop students' cognitive activity for independent thinking, research, problem solving and learning.

It has been determined that the model developed in the study will be implemented in the following stages:

1. *Diagnostic stage* - the current level of knowledge, state of thinking, motivation of students are determined. Based on special tests, questionnaires, interviews.

2. *Targeted developmental stage* - classes are organized based on an individual approach to the needs of each student. Tasks requiring cognitive activity, game methods, group projects are introduced.

3. *Activity-reflective stage* - students analyze their achievements, develop skills of expressing their opinions, critical analysis and problem solving.

4. *Control and correction stage* - the obtained results are analyzed, shortcomings are identified and adjustments are made to the educational process. The dynamics of the development of the student's cognitive activity is assessed individually.

The developed model is based on the requirements of today's digitalized society, and each component of the model has its own specific purpose. The goals set in each component serve the implementation of the general goal. The model is based on the organization of primary education and the process of developing cognitive activity in students. In this process, one of the pedagogical technologies considered effective in the current educational environment - the "Flipped Classroom" technology - is aimed at revealing the didactic possibilities of developing students' cognitive activity.

The initial component of the model is goal-motivational, and at this stage it is important to set a specific goal. Because the effectiveness of subsequent processes is based on this. The goal-motivational component of the model for developing cognitive activity in primary school students is the main component that determines the pedagogical conditions and mechanisms that awaken students' internal needs for knowledge, create interest in learning, seek knowledge and encourage active thinking. This component is manifested as a system that determines the strategic direction of education and activates active cognitive processes through motivation and personal needs.

I. The content of the goal-motivational component is as follows:

1. Setting the main goals of cognitive development.
2. Awakening and supporting internal and external motivation.
3. Creating conditions that arouse interest in knowledge.
4. Personal goals that attract the student to activity.
5. Positive emotional environment and incentive mechanisms.

The goal-motivational component is the main stage that serves to form a positive attitude of the student to learning, to develop him as a conscious, interested and active participant. Through this component, the student's internal activity, intellectual need and conscious participation in the process of acquiring knowledge are ensured.

II. The activity-content component is a component that covers pedagogical aspects related to the organization of practical educational activities and the formation of content that ensure the cognitive activity of students. It is aimed at developing students' independence in acquiring knowledge, thinking skills, attitude to problem situations, and skills of analysis and generalization.

The following tasks were identified to ensure the implementation of this component in accordance with the established goal:

- ensuring that students' cognitive activity is consistent, systematic and active;
- directing the content of education to cognitive activity: observation, comparison, analysis, drawing conclusions;
- selecting the content of education based on tasks that ensure the activity of each student;
- consolidating knowledge by linking it to real life.

In the primary school “Mother Language and Reading Literacy” lessons, the following types of activities were identified in the research work to develop the cognitive activity of students and to organize a developing learning environment (see Table 1):

Table 1

Learning activities that develop cognitive activity types

Types of activities	Cognitive goal
Observation	Attention to detail, ability to clarify issues.
Comparison	Generalization and differentiation of objects, systematization of their properties
Analysis and synthesis	To isolate the specific characteristics of a situation or process, and to combine parts based on similar aspects.
Sorting and grouping	Identifying underlying categories and developing logical structures from within the data.
To predict (forecast)	Making assumptions based on previous experiences.
Problem solving	Seeking and finding optimal solutions to presented problems through analytical thinking.

Each method and form serves to activate the student's cognitive abilities such as thinking, memory, analytical skills, comparison, guessing, generalization. Based on this, we will consider the conditions for using the above-selected methods and forms in the lessons of "Mother Language and Reading Literacy" (Table 2).

Table 2

Methods used in the lesson of "Mother Language and Reading Literacy" and their potential for developing cognitive activity

Method name	Practical example (based on the topic)	Type of cognitive activity
<i>Problem-Based Learning (PBL)</i>	Topic: "Sentence and its types" → Give students incorrectly constructed sentences and solve the problem based on the question "Why is there an error in this sentence?"	Analysis, understanding, comparison

Question and answer chain	Topic: “Noun, adjective, verb” → The teacher says one word (“tree”), each student continues with the related words in the grammatical category (“green”, “grows”)	Identifying categories, logical connections
Mind map	Topic: "Composing a text about natural phenomena" → In the center is the word "Spring", and around it, students write sentences based on words related to the central word.	Associative thinking, structural understanding
Compose a crossword puzzle	Topic: “Spelling rules” → Letters are given, students find the correctly spelled words from the given letters	Memory, thinking, choice
Analysis through experience	Topic: “Sentence structure” → Different words are given, students arrange them in different orders to make sentences and analyze what difference in meaning there is	Syntactic analysis, cause and effect
Role play (dramatization)	Topic: “Erkatay Text” → Students read the text expressively and understand its essence by playing the roles of characters	Emotional intelligence, figurative thinking
Brainstorming	Topic: “Describing the image of a hero” → Students answer the question “What actions make him a positive hero?”	Quick thinking, putting forward ideas
Graphic organizers (Venn diagram, flowchart)	Topic: “Comparing adjectives and verbs” → Reflecting similarities and differences in a T-chart	Comparison, generalization
To predict (forecast)	Topic: “Completing the text” → The beginning of the text is read, students complete it by guessing its continuation	Creativity, creative thinking

It can be seen from the table that the selection of various methods aimed at activating students in the lesson, based on the content of the topics, ensures their cognitive activity. The methods are applied to the lesson process in different ways, depending on their application. This is based on the students' enthusiasm, needs, level of knowledge and pedagogical improvisation (Table 3).

Table 3

Forms of application of methods that develop cognitive activity

Shape	Application (within the framework of mother tongue and reading literacy)	Cognitive outcome
<i>Individual work</i>	Write independent answers to 3 questions based on the text	Independent thinking, interpretation
<i>Working in pairs</i>	Complete the end of the story in pairs and tell it to each other	Exchange of ideas, cooperation

<i>Group work</i>	"Qualitative Sentence" project in groups - each group composes a sentence based on the given words and explains it	Decision-making, reasoning
<i>General discussion with the class</i>	Together, find the main idea of the text and evaluate the characters' actions.	Participation in communication, understanding and acceptance of ideas

Based on the classifications given, it can be said that the formation and development of cognitive activity of primary school students is one of the priority areas of modern education. In particular, in the subject "Native Language and Reading Literacy" such tasks as activating students' thinking, developing logical thinking, and forming independent research skills are implemented within the framework of the activity-content component. This component links the content of educational activities not only with the acquisition of ready-made knowledge, but also with students' thinking, analysis, generalization, and consistent and active acquisition of new knowledge.

III. Technological component. This component is a system of technological organization of educational activities aimed at developing students' cognitive activity and includes the integral integration of teaching methods, interactive tools, information and communication technologies (ICT), educational environment, forms of training, and control mechanisms.

The technological component serves to enrich the educational process with modern means, adapt it to the cognitive needs and individual characteristics of the student, and more effectively form cognitive activity. Thanks to this component, learning is organized as an interactive activity aimed not only at transferring knowledge, but also at conscious search, reflective thinking and managing one's own learning process.

The technological component, in its essence, takes the lesson process beyond the simple transfer of information and ensures that the student becomes an active subject of independent learning and knowledge acquisition. This, in turn, activates higher-level cognitive actions, such as analysis, research, asking questions, guessing and putting forward new ideas in acquiring knowledge.

IV. The resulting component is the final stage of the model, which serves to identify, evaluate and analyze the results of pedagogical activities carried out to develop the cognitive activity of students, and to determine future educational strategies on their basis. This component monitors the effectiveness of learning, the dynamics of individual growth and the results corresponding to the competence-based approach.

Tools and forms for assessing the cognitive activity of primary school students (Table 4):

Table 4

1. Format evaluation (process)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – oral questions and answers, written comments, feedback, daily reflections; – observation sheets, activity logs; – quick tasks given during the training.
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2. Summative assessment (final)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – determining the student's level of knowledge based on assignments; – interdisciplinary integrated tests, project work; – justifying one's opinion, textual developments (story, expression, analysis).
3. Diagnostic assessment (initial and monitoring)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – analytical tests conducted at the beginning and end of the lesson; – observation maps reflecting the dynamics of student change.
4. Self-assessment and reflection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Engaging the student in conscious learning based on questions such as “What did I learn today?”, “What problem did I face?”, “What solution did I find?”; – Self-awareness using colored signal cards, assessment stickers, and emotional cards.

When determining the cognitive activity of students, the level of activity, independence, depth, and ability to reflect in their cognitive activities are selected as criteria. The following levels are distinguished based on the behavior observed in students' learning activities:

Levels of development of cognitive activity	Features of being visible
<i>Primary (reproductive) level</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – memorizes only ready-made knowledge; – answers questions only based on the material seen; – tends to repeat rather than think; – remains disoriented in problematic situations; – asks few or no questions.
<i>Medium (partially constructive) level</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – has partial independence in acquiring knowledge; – understands the problem, but requires guidance for a solution; – asks questions, but needs help finding the answer; – is still weak in expressing his/her thoughts.
<i>Well-developed (constructive) level</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – independently acquires knowledge and can apply it in practice; – independently analyzes the problem, offers several solutions; – asks questions related to the topic, puts forward new ideas; – substantiates his/her opinion consistently, with evidence and examples; – has developed skills such as text analysis, generalization, and comparison.

<i>Creative (creative-cognitive) level</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">– is ready to analyze and synthesize knowledge;– creates new ideas, solves problems innovatively;– asks independent questions and reflects on them;– defends his or her own opinion with justification, is tolerant of opposing opinions;– interprets what he or she has read, relating it to life experience.
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Within the framework of this pedagogical model, the first component, the goal-motivational part, serves to form an internal need for knowledge in students, to express a conscious attitude to the learning process. At this stage, by identifying students' interests, stimulating them, and encouraging them to ask questions, their internal motivation is strengthened. As a result, students begin to participate not in a passive attitude towards knowledge, but as active research subjects.

The second activity-content component of the model provides for the content organization of educational activities aimed at developing students' intellectual activity. Through the use of problem-based learning, mind mapping, question-and-answer chains, dramatization, and other interactive methods in lessons, students are involved in performing cognitive activities such as independent thinking, analysis, generalization, comparison, and guessing. This approach forms the skills of students to deeply understand the subject, actively work on information, and express their opinions with justification.

The third technological component ensures the interactivity of the educational process through the use of modern pedagogical technologies and information and communication tools. Flipped classroom, project-based learning, ICT tools, digital resources, electronic assessment systems put students at the center of the learning process. This increases their ability to independently search, visually perceive knowledge, and apply their knowledge in a modern environment.

The fourth outcome component of the model determines the levels of development of cognitive activity, develops assessment criteria, and monitors the dynamics of individual growth of students. At this stage, the quality of knowledge acquisition, level of thinking, and intellectual development of the student are determined through format, summative, diagnostic, and reflective assessment tools.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this pedagogical model serves to effectively develop the cognitive potential of students based on a step-by-step approach. Each component is integrally integrated, and their harmony allows the student to be formed as an active, knowledgeable, inquisitive, and independent-thinking individual. This creates the basis for the implementation of a modern and effective educational model that meets the requirements of the competency-based approach.

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